

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms RESHMA SURESH bearing USN6SU21FS801 has completed his/her internship at in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SANDRA FERNANDES SELESTIN bearing USN6SU21FS802 has completed his/her internship at in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms VAISHNAVI R.J bearing USN6SU21FS803 has completed his/her internship at in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsSAGILA bearing USN6SU21FS804 has completed his/her internship at in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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